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Numerical and experimental study of forming limit diagrams during single point incremental forming for Al/Ti/Al sheets

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Abstract

This article investigates the limit forming diagram (FLD) for three-layer aluminum sheets 1050 and titanium grade 1/aluminum 1050. This examination uses a combination of numerical and experimental approaches through a single-point incremental forming (SPIF) process. First, the 3-layer sheet was produced by a cold roll bonding process with 50% strain. First, the 3-layer sheets were fabricated using the cold bond rolling technique with a 50% rolling reduction. In the following, the effects of the tool diameter parameters, Step down, and feed rate were investigated experimentally and numerically by considering the design of the experiment method on the FLD, the thickness distribution, and the forming depth. The results showed that by increasing the diameter of the tool from 6 mm to 9 mm, the formability improved, while with the increase in the step-down, the formability decreased. The thickness distribution test was done experimentally and numerically, and the simulation results agreed with the experiment.

Keywords: Single-Point Incremental Forming, Limit Forming Diagram, Cold Rolling, Finite Element Analysis, Multilayer Metal Sheets.

1. Introduction

Incremental Sheet Forming (ISF) is a swift prototyping technique for crafting components of diverse configurations using sheet metal. This method exhibits remarkable adaptability and leads to noteworthy reductions in both cost and time. The art of sheet metal forming is used to forge many products, including household appliance casings, automotive components, aerospace constructs, and items within the food industry.

The initial concept of Incremental Sheet Forming (ISF) was first introduced in the United States by Roux in 1960 [1]. Furthermore, the ISF method was patented by Luszak in 1967 [2]. However, due to the limitations of CNC machines during that era, this method received much attention in the early 1990s, particularly in Japan. In 1994, Matsumara [3]. They started using this method for forming and manufacturing parts from sheet metal. With the advancement of CNC machines, the pace of growth and development of ISF has accelerated, and recently, it has gained recognition among researchers. Research conducted by experts indicates that the flexibility of the ISF method surpasses that of traditional forming processes [4]. There are several methods available for assessing formability in incremental sheet forming. Forming angle and FLD can be employed to measure sheet metal formability [5]. The maximum forming

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angle (ϕ_{max}) at which the sheet can be formed without tearing is called the limit forming angle [6]. Cold-roll bonding is widely acknowledged as one of the most crucial and practical methods for manufacturing two-layer and multilayer sheets [7]. Jalali et al. [8] determined that the maximum forming angle for a brass/aluminum sample was 60 degrees, and for an aluminum/brass sample, it was less than 57.5 degrees. Kumar et al. [9] demonstrated that formability increases as wall angle and step size are reduced. They also observed that combining a smaller step size with a lower wall angle significantly enhances formability. Kim and Park [10] examined various tools for forming and found that ball-end tools are more effective than hemisphere-end tools in terms of formability. The optimal formability is achieved with a 10-millimeter tool. Choudhar and Mulay [11] used the variance analysis method to investigate the effect of ISF parameters on formability. They used three aluminum grades, 1050, 6061, and 7075, in their experiments and showed that in addition to forming parameters such as tool diameter and vertical pitch, the sheet material also affects the amount of formability. Caliskan et al. [12] investigated the effect of wall angle and step-down on surface quality and thickness distribution in the ISF process by the Taguchi method. Their results showed that the surface quality decreases with decreasing step-down. Honarpisheh et al. [13] studied the impact of various process parameters, including wall angle, step size, and tool diameter, on the formability, forming force, and thickness distribution of the test specimens in electrically heated incremental forming (EHIF) on Ti-6Al-4V alloy sheets. They found that increasing the step size and decreasing the tool diameter resulted in heightened forming forces during EHIF. Esmailian et al. [14] investigated the effect of SPIF parameters on the formability of 3-layer sheets by surface response method (RSM) and reported the optimal parameters to increase formability. Sakhtemanian et al. [15] studied the effects of layer arrangement and step-down on formability and forming force for a 2-layer Ti/St sheet in the SPIF process. Their results showed that the forming force would increase by increasing the vertical step. Zaba et al. [7] studied the effect of step-down on the formability of a 2-layer Al/Cu sheet. They showed that the formability decreased by increasing the vertical step to 1.1 mm. Rezaei et al. [16] studied the effect of SPIF forming parameters on the formability of a 2-layer St/Ti sheet. They showed that the step-down significantly affects the thickness distribution and formability. Yoganjaneyulu et al. [17] investigated the tool's step-down and rotational speed effect on the titanium sheet's formability. They showed that increasing the tool diameter from 8 mm to 12 mm would increase the fracture strain. The results for the rotational speed indicated the increase in sheet formability with increasing tool rotational speed. Tayebi et al [18] conducted his studies for 2-layer Al/Cu sheet by three tool paths: cone, square pyramid and straight groove, and showed that the formability is higher for the cone tool path. Also, several researchers researched the formability of single-layer titanium sheets. They presented their results to increase the formability of single-layer titanium sheets by the SPIF process [19-22]. Multilayer sheets, which consist of two or more layers of different metals stacked together to form a composite material, offer a range of advantageous properties. These properties include improved formability, high mechanical strength coupled with flexibility, enhanced resistance to corrosion and wear, superior sound and vibration damping, even temperature distribution, reduced spring back, and wrinkling. All these characteristics ultimately lead to lower weight and reduced component production costs.

Considering the studies conducted on aluminum-titanium multilayer sheets, limited studies have been conducted on the formability of three-layer aluminum-titanium samples produced by the SPIF process. In this research paper, three-layer sheets of AA 1050/Titanium Grade 1/AA 1050 were manufactured through a cold roll bonding process. The study involved applying the incremental sheet forming (ISF) process and utilizing Abaqus software for finite element analysis. This paper innovatively investigated the forming

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parameters through the design of experimental tests on the formability values of a 3-layer aluminum/titanium sheet. The investigation also delved into key parameters like tool diameter, feed rate, and tool step size in the ISF. The research further encompasses the visualization of factors such as thickness distribution, forming depth, fracture limit angle, and the distinctive limit forming diagram specific to the single-point incremental sheet forming (ISF) process for the three-layer AA 1050/Titanium Grade 1/AA 1050 sheets. Additionally, the numerical simulation results were scrutinized and validated using experimental data to ascertain the simulation's accuracy

2- Experimental work

2-1- The cold roll bonding process

Aluminum 1050 and Titanium Grade 1 with a consistent 0.8 mm thickness were used to manufacture three-layer sheets. The chemical composition of Aluminum and Titanium is presented in Table 1 and Table 2. The chemical properties are obtained based on the quantum-metric test. A cold roll bonding process was employed to produce the three-layer sheets. In this process, rolling plays a pivotal role in achieving severe plastic deformation and establishing a cohesive connection among the three sheets, creating a fully integrated sheet. Initially, the sheets were cut with 130×70 mm. So, before commencing the cold roll bonding process, the Aluminum sheets underwent annealing in heat treatment furnace at 400° for 60 minutes, while the Titanium sheets were annealed at 650° for 120 minute. The sheets were soaked in an industrial acetone solution for 10 minutes to prepare the sheet surfaces and eliminate surface contaminants. To achieve a strong bond between the sheets, they underwent wire brushing using a steel wire brush affixed to a handheld drill.

Additionally, to prevent slippage and ensure proper alignment of the sheets during the rolling process, holes were drilled at the four corners beneath the rollers, and the three Al/Ti/Al sheets were stacked on top of each other with copper wire threaded through them. The roller possessed a diameter of 400 millimeters and rotated at a speed of rpm. Following a single rolling stage with a 50% reduction in thickness, three-layer Al/Ti/Al samples with a final thickness of 1.2 millimeters were successfully manufactured.

Table 1. Chemical composition of commercially pure aluminum sheet 1050 (weight percent)

Al	Fe	Si	Cu	Mn	Mg	Zn
99.32	0.246	0.176	0.0098	0.0763	0.0286	0.0171
Ni	V	Ti	Ca	Cr	Pb	Sn
0.0040	0.0213	0.0184	0.0021	0.0034	0.0033	0.0050

Table 2. Chemical composition of grade 1 pure titanium sheet (weight percent)

Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Pd
99.6	0.0054	0.0054	0.0140	0.0156
Fe	Mo	Sn	Si	Ru
0.0316	0.0161	0.0255	0.0144	0.0434

2-2- Mechanical properties

• Tensile test by DIC method

As depicted in Fig.1, we prepared these sheets in compliance with ASTM-E8 standards using a wire-cutting machine. The tensile tests were conducted using an STM-50 SANTAM machine equipped with DIC testing tools, and the strain rate was considered 1 mm/min. The multilayer samples were annealed to eliminate the effect of work hardening after the rolling process. The three separate samples of three-layer sheets were completely annealed in heat treatment furnace at temperatures of 400°, 450°, and 500° for 90 minutes to obtain the annealing temperature of aluminum and titanium sheets. A tensile test was performed for each of the three annealing conditions. Then, analyzing the results of the tensile test (in terms of strength and ductility), the annealing temperature and time were selected for the 3-layer sample at 500°C for 90 minutes. Furthermore, to determine the strain hardening coefficients, we conducted tensile tests on three-layer samples annealed in rolling straight 45° and 90° directions relative to the rolling direction.

• Micro Vickers hardness test

The specimens were utilized for the micro-hardness examination to assess the effect of annealing for Al and Ti sheets. Subsequently, these specimens underwent grinding and polishing to attain a uniformly smooth surface. A conical indenter was employed to exert a 100-gram load on the surface for 15 seconds through micro-hardness testing. This indentation process followed a triangular pattern, carried out at a minimum of three distinct points on the surface to minimize potential measurement inaccuracies.

2-3- SPIF Process

SPIF process was performed to obtain FLD for base and multilayer sheets. Furthermore, before the forming process, we applied a circular pattern with a 2.5-millimeter diameter to mark the surface of the samples for grid purposes. This research used the spherical head type of tool to reduce the friction between the sheets and the tool [18]. The material used to make the tools was VCN 150 alloy steel. The SPIF process was done by selecting three types of tools with 6, 9, and 12 mm diameters to investigate the effect of tool diameter on the FLD and thickness distribution (Fig.2). The tool path movement to perform the forming process was considered as a spiral path and were established using Power-mill software (Fig.3). The reason for this choice is the higher malleability of the spiral tool [19]. Also, the rotational speed of the tool in this study was chosen to be 700 rpm. The setup related to the experimental SPIF test is shown in Fig 4. The FLD will be measured to determine the forming limit angle in the experimental test according to eq.1 when the first crack is seen in the formed part. Where h_p represents the deformation depth at the failure point, R corresponds to the variable wall curve radius, and H denotes the total forming height. Here, the value of H has been assumed to be 96.57 mm.

$$\psi_{\max} = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{H-h_p}{R}\right) \quad (1)$$

After the SPIF process is finished, the circular markings initially present on the outer surface of the three-layer sheet have changed into elliptical shapes. To measure the FLD, calculate the corresponding minor

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and major strains for the diagram using equations (2) and (3), respectively. D_1 and D_2 are the sizes of the major and minor oval diameters, respectively, and D_0 is equal to the circle's diameter before shaping to 2.5 mm.

$$\varepsilon_1 = \ln\left(\frac{D_1}{D_0}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \ln\left(\frac{D_2}{D_0}\right) \quad (3)$$

Fig.1. (a) Al 1050 and Ti single-layer tensile test samples annealed, (b) three-layer samples in the zero-degree direction of rolling and annealed at three different temperatures for 90 minutes, and a cold-worked sample in the rolling direction, (c) three-layer samples in the direction of 45 and 90 degrees to the rolling. (d) Random gridding of tensile test specimens

Fig.2: Tools with 6, 9, and 12 mm diameters.

Fig.3: (a) Tool path determination, (b) Final part model with variable wall angle.

Fig.4 : performing the SPIF process by CNC milling machine.

2.4- Experimental design

This study used the response surface method (RSM) with the Box-Behnken design (BBD) methodology with two central replicates to enhance process efficiency. The experimental designs were generated using Design Expert software. Table 3 shows the specific parameter ranges for the input variables in the experimental tests, and provides details of the experimental test layout in Table 4.

Table 3. Selection range of input parameters in the experimental test

input parameter	Forming parameters		
Tool diameter (mm)	6	9	12
Tool pitch (mm)	0.2	0.6	1
Feed rate (mm/min)	500	700	900

Table 4. Design of experimental experiments

Test number	Step Down (mm)	Feed rate (mm/min)	Tool diameter (mm)
1	1	500	9
2	0.6	700	9
3	0.6	700	9
4	1	900	9
5	0.2	500	9
6	0.2	900	9
7	0.6	900	6
8	0.6	500	6
9	0.2	700	6

10	1	700	6
11	0.2	700	12
12	1	700	12
13	0.6	900	12
14	0.6	500	12

2.5- Thickness distribution

Additionally, to analyze the thickness distribution within the formed sheet, first, the sample was divided into two halves using a saw tool. The cut section was carefully polished using an abrasive sander affixed to a pedestal to refine the edges and eliminate any irregularities. Following this preparation, precise measurements of the sheet's thickness were taken at specified locations on the outer surface of the sample using a micrometer, according to Fig.5.

Fig.5. Measurement of thickness distribution for formed samples.

3- Finite Element Method Analysis

This research utilized the ABAQUS Explicit software to simulate the SPIF process. As shown in Fig 6-a flowchart of the simulation and Fig.6-b, the simulation encompassed three components: the sheet, the holder, and the tools, all modeled in three dimensions based on their geometric dimensions as per the experimental tests can be seen. The sheet was represented as a deformable shell, while the other components were defined as rigid bodies. Material properties, including Poisson's ratio, elastic modulus, plastic properties, and density, were specified for the deformable sheet using the Property module. Furthermore, true stress-strain data was used to define the plastic properties. The anisotropy properties of the sheet for the two-layer samples were determined according to equation 5. Given the extensive deformation and contact interactions between the tool and the sheet within the Step module, the explicit dynamic solver was chosen to perform the simulation process. A mass scaling factor 100,000 was applied to expedite problem-solving time and enhance computational efficiency. The ratio of kinetic energy and total energy was checked, and this value was found to be less than 5% to check the effect of mass scaling on simulation accuracy [20]. Surface-to-surface contact was used to define contact interactions between the sheet and the rigid tool and between the sheet and the die. These interactions encompassed normal and tangential contact behaviors, with a friction coefficient 0.1 assumed between surfaces [24]. The spindle speed set the tool's rotational speed to 3.73 radians per second. Generally, the tool path in all three directions was determined

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individually using G-code derived from the Power-mill software. This was accomplished by transferring the extracted tool path G-code from Power-mill to Matlab and running the Matlab code, which provided the coordinates of the tool's center points in all three directions with a specified time interval. Partitioning the sheet is a strategy to reduce computational time while preserving simulation accuracy and optimizing the required elements. This research used the Structured Mesh technique with a quadrilateral mesh to mesh the sheet in the ABAQUS/Explicit module. As depicted in Fig.7, the sheet was meshed using 8678 elements of the reduced integration shell-type S4R elements.

Fig.6: a) The flowchart of the simulation, b) How to assemble the tool, sheet, and holder in the gradual forming process.

Fig.7: S4R type mesh used for three-layer sheet.

4- Results and Discussion

This section presents the result of micro-hardness and tensile tests, along with the analysis of thickness distribution, deformation depth, forming limit angle, and FLD of the SPIF process applied to the Al/Ti/Al three-layer sheet. Additionally, the numerical simulation results using the finite element method were compared and validated against the experimental findings.

4-1- Micro-hardness Evaluation

Vickers Micro-hardness tests were conducted up to four repetitions for pure Al and Ti samples and the penetration depth area. The hardness test was performed for the base sheet samples in two states before and after annealing to investigate the effect of annealing temperature on the hardness value. The resulting average values of these tests are recorded as the final results and are presented in Table 5. It can be seen that the hardness of the base samples decreases after the annealing process. The decrease in hardness in the annealed samples is due to the reduction of the work-hardening effect and the increase in the grain size in the microstructure and dynamic recovery [20]. Micro-hardness measurement was done for 3-layer samples in the penetration zone. It was observed that the hardness obtained in the penetration zone is between the hardness of the Al and Ti base plate, which indicates that the 3-layer samples are affected by the rolling process and the increase in dislocation density [25].

Table 5. The selection range of the input parameters in the micro Vickers test

Name of the piece	test 1 (HV)	test 2 (HV)	test 3 (HV)	test 4 (HV)	Average difficulty
aluminum	56.70	54.86	55.83	—	55.79
annealed aluminum	49.08	48.3	47.96	—	48.45
Titanium	160	162	156	159	159.25

Annealed titanium	155	154	151	153	153.25
Penetration area	143	150	149	152	148.5

2-4- Uniaxial Tensile Test

In this study, Digital Image Correlation (DIC) uniaxial tensile tests were employed to investigate the mechanical properties of the base and three-layer sheets and to facilitate a comparative analysis. Fig.8 displays the engineering stress-strain curves of the three-layer sample in the rolling direction at four different temperatures: ambient temperature, 400°, 450°, and 500° [20,21]. As shown in Fig.8, the stress-strain curve of the three-layer sample at ambient temperature exhibited higher tensile strength and reduced elongation due to work hardening during the rolling process and a 50% reduction in thickness compared to the other samples. Furthermore, the sample tested at 500° displayed the lowest tensile strength and the highest elongation. The increase in formability at higher annealing temperatures can be attributed to the activation of dislocation mechanisms climb and grain boundary sliding at higher temperatures. These quantitative variations are detailed in Table 6. and Fig.9 illustrates the engineering stress-strain curves of annealed base sheets of Al and Ti samples and three-layer samples tested at 0, 45, and 90 degrees relative to the rolling direction at 500°. Notably, the Ti sample demonstrated the highest tensile strength and elongation, while the Al sample exhibited the lowest tensile strength and elongation. The tensile test results confirm the hardness test results. The results showed that the tensile strength of the 3-layer sample is between the strength of Al and Ti [28]. The results indicated that the three-layer sample of Al/Ti/Al has higher strength and ductility than the Al base sheet, which showed the capability of the Al/Ti/Al mechanical connection [29]. The reason for the decrease in the length and strength of the multilayer sample compared to Ti can be considered as the strain hardening in the rolling process. Fine graining and small grain boundaries also create obstacles to dislocation movement, leading to strain reduction [26]. The mechanical properties of annealed single-layer aluminum and titanium samples, each tested with two repetitions, are outlined in Table 7, and the mechanical properties of three-layer samples at 0, 45, and 90 degrees relative to the rolling direction are summarized in Table 8.

Fig.8. The engineering stress-strain diagrams of samples in the rolling direction with four ambient temperatures: 400, 450, and 500 degrees.

Table 6. Result of tensile test for tree layer sheet in four different temperatures

Three-layer sample	ultimate strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Stress changes compared to ambient temperature (%)	Strain changes compared to ambient temperature (%)
Cooled work at ambient temperature	336.4	6.14	0	0
Annealed at 400 degrees	239.9	16.03	-28.69	161.07
Annealed at 450 degrees	235.4	20.94	-42.90	241.04
Annealed at 500 degrees	226.5	23.97	-48.52	290.39

Fig.9. Engineering stress-strain diagram of the samples in the direction of 0, 45, and 90 degrees for the base sheet of annealed Al and Ti samples

Table 7. Mechanical properties of aluminum and titanium tensile test samples with two replicates

Single layer sample	E (GPa)	$\sigma_{UTS} (1)$ (MPa)	El% ₍₁₎	$\sigma_{UTS} (2)$ (MPa)	El% ₍₂₎	$\sigma_{UTS} (AVG)$ (MPa)	El% _(AVG)
annealed aluminum	67	112	12.46	117.5	11.58	114.75	12.02
Annealed titanium	58	343.6	45.25	339.9	44.83	341.75	45.04

Table 8. Mechanical properties of tensile samples in the direction of 0, 45, and 90 degrees compared to rolling

Sheet	σ_{UTS} (MPa)	El%	σ_y (MPa)	R_{θ} vlaue	$\Delta\sigma_{UTS} (\%)$	$\Delta El\%_{(0\%)}$
RD (0°)	226.5	23.97	175	1.27	0	0
ND (45°)	223.1	25.53	188	1.48	-1.50	6.51
TD (90°)	221.9	18.05	200	1.68	-2.03	-24.69

The plastic anisotropy observed in metal sheets, which results from the development of crystal orientations during the rolling process, is quantified using the anisotropy coefficient denoted as R in Eq.4.

$$R = \frac{\varepsilon_w}{\varepsilon_t} = \frac{\varepsilon_w}{-(\varepsilon_w + \varepsilon_l)} \quad (4)$$

In Eq.1, ε_w , ε_t , and ε_l signify the strains in the width, thickness, and lengthwise directions, respectively, recorded during uniaxial tensile testing after a 10 to 20 percent change in relative length. An R-value greater than 1 suggests a propensity for increased resistance to thickness reduction and higher yield strength. Additionally, the normal anisotropy coefficient is derived using Eq.5.

$$\bar{R} = \frac{R_0 + 2R_{45} + R_{90}}{4} = 1.47 \quad (5)$$

Furthermore, to ascertain the strain hardening exponent (n) and the strength coefficient (k) of the sheet in the rolling direction, the structural equation $\sigma = k\varepsilon^n$ is applied. This involves utilizing the plastic region of the true stress-strain curve, as illustrated in

0, and fitting the appropriate curve using logarithmic coordinates to calculate the values of n and k (n=0.1071, k=320.08).

Fig.10: a) True stress-strain diagram of the three-layer sheet in the rolling direction, b) Flow stress in logarithmic coordinates.

3-4- Experimental Analysis of SPIF process

The formed three-layer samples were done according to the determined Experimental design, and the results are shown in Fig.11. The circular marks on the outer sheet surfaces have transformed into ellipses. We are applying various forming parameters to the sheets, as described by Eq.2 and 3 and measuring these ellipses' major and minor axes at points near the fracture. Then, we could determine the sheets' Forming Limit Diagrams (FLD). The FLD₀ point ($\epsilon_2=0$), positioned along the limit strain line (measured from the plot's origin), serves as a formability criterion. The FLD diagrams resulting from experimental data are depicted in Fig.12.

The forming limit angle for the formed samples, according to Eq.1, will be obtained with the forming depth. The results obtained for the forming limit angle can be seen in Table 9. The thickness distribution for the formed samples was done along the wall with a variable angle (Fig.16), and the results were obtained by examining the effect of the SPIF parameters on the lowest thickness distribution shown in Fig.17. By reviewing the results obtained from the SPIF parameters for forming depth, forming limit angle, and minimum thickness, it can be seen that the highest formability value is for sample number 5. The parameters obtained from the experimental test for this sample show that 0.2mm for step down, 500 mm for feed rate, and 9 mm tool diameter have obtained the highest formability for three-layer samples [27]. Also, the lowest formability is for sample number 12. It can be seen that all three parameters of step down, feed rate, and tool diameter have increased compared to the sample number 5 parameters. As the diameter of the tool increases, the contact surface between the tool and the sheet increases, which causes the shear and tensile stress of the contact area between the tool and the sheet to increase, as a result of which the possibility of thinning and failure increases [32]. To analyze the effect of SPIF parameters in the Design Expert software,

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the results of Table.9 are defined as the input and output of the software. To statistically investigate the effect of SPIF parameters and estimate the relationship between them, the regression model of linear combination with square has been used. In Analysis of variance (ANOVA) analysis, the lower the value of P ($P \leq 0.05$) and the higher the value of F, the higher the validity of the model [28,29]. By checking Table 10, It can be concluded that the impact of all three parameters of diameter, step down, and tool feed rate is effective on the formability ($P \leq 0.0001$), and the interaction between the variables is also significant ($P \leq 0.05$). In Fig.13, the normality of the residuals was checked from the data scatter plot, and the results indicate the model and experimental data normality. By studying Fig.14 and Fig.15, it can be seen that the effect of the tool diameter factor on FLD is stronger than the other two factors. In other words, by increasing the tool diameter from 6 mm to 9 mm, the FLD has increased. Increasing the tool diameter to an optimal level increases the contact surface of the tool and the sheet, and the local heat caused by friction improves formability. Also, increasing the step-down leads to a decrease in formability [35]. However, the feed rate parameter has the least effect on the formability; in this case, the feed rate can be increased to increase the forming speed in the SPIF process.

Fig.11. Three-layer samples formed with variable wall angle

Fig.12. FLD diagrams of experimental tests No. 1 to 14.

Table 9. Result of Experimental design for three-layer samples

Test number	Tool pitch (mm)	Advance rate (mm/min)	Tool diameter (mm)	Forming depth (mm)	break wall angle (deg)	Minimum thickness t_f (mm)	Percentage of thickness reduction (%)	Maximum principal strain (FLD0)
1	1	500	9	24	55.5	0.77	35.8	0.494
2	0.6	700	9	24.78	56.4	0.74	38.3	0.521
3	0.6	700	9	24.82	56.5	0.74	38.3	0.522
4	1	900	9	21.98	53.1	0.81	32.5	0.428
5	0.2	500	9	25.32	57	0.72	40	0.532
6	0.2	900	9	24.36	55.9	0.74	38.3	0.520
7	0.6	900	6	21.4	52.4	0.81	32.5	0.411
8	0.6	500	6	22.06	53.2	0.79	34.2	0.440
9	0.2	700	6	22.92	54.3	0.78	35	0.464
10	1	700	6	20.74	51.7	0.84	30	0.407
11	0.2	700	12	20.16	50.9	0.84	30	0.393
12	1	700	12	18.52	48.9	0.88	26.6	0.317
13	0.6	900	12	18.78	49.2	0.87	27.5	0.322
14	0.6	500	12	19.44	50	0.86	28.3	0.366

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Table 10. Analysis of variance with the acceptable p-value

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	0.0704	9	0.0078	5960.63	< 0.0001	significant
A-Tool	0.0131	1	0.0131	9997.71	< 0.0001	
B-Step	0.0086	1	0.0086	6587.52	< 0.0001	
C-FeedRate	0.0029	1	0.0029	2171.52	< 0.0001	
AB	0.0001	1	0.0001	68.76	0.0012	
AC	0.0001	1	0.0001	42.86	0.0028	
BC	0.0007	1	0.0007	555.43	< 0.0001	
A ²	0.0442	1	0.0442	33660.95	< 0.0001	
B ²	0.0002	1	0.0002	186.67	0.0002	
C ²	0.0012	1	0.0012	903.47	< 0.0001	
Residual	5.250E-06	4	1.313E-06			
Lack of Fit	4.750E-06	3	1.583E-06	3.17	0.3866	not significant
Pure Error	5.000E-07	1	5.000E-07			
Cor Total	0.0704	13				

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Fig.13 .Normal Plot of Residuals for three-layer samples

a)

b)

c)

Fig. 14. Interaction of parameters for three-layer sample on FLD, a) Step down and tool diameter, b) Feed rate and step down, C) tool diameter and Feed rate

Fig. 15. Deviation plot of the data for the FLD_0

4-4- Thickness Distribution and Comparative Analysis of Experimental and Numerical Forming Limit Diagrams

In this section, simulation outcomes are presented and subsequently compared with experimental findings to ensure result accuracy. Fig. 16 represents the necking region in the experimental test and finite element simulation, illustrating the plastic strain distribution. This particular region is highly vulnerable to sheet cracking or tearing.

Following this, as illustrated in Fig. 17, contour plots depicting simulated thickness corresponding to test numbers are presented. These contour plots are determined at the fracture depth, as identified in the experimental tests. Given that test numbers 2 and 3 represent experiments conducted under identical conditions and parameters, the simulation was performed only once for numerical analysis.

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Fig.16. Comparison of the throat area of the cut sheet in the experimental investigation of sample number one and numerical simulation

Fig.17. Sheet thickness distribution contours in finite element simulation

Furthermore, in Fig. 18, present FLD using experimental and numerical methods. It's important to highlight that the formability assessment relies on localized necking as the criterion in the numerical simulation. Consequently, in the experimental process, the formability criterion will be evaluated with the failure FLD, while in the numerical analysis, the thinning-based FLD is used as the formability criterion, and a comparison is conducted accordingly.

c)

d)

Fig.18. The comparison of the FLD in the SPIF process for three-layer sheets in the experimental and numerical methods, a) R1-R4,b) R5-R7, c) R8-R10, d) R11-R12, e) R13-R14

Through an examination of Fig 18, it becomes feasible to utilize the outcomes of numerical analysis to establish an acceptable safety margin for industrial and manufacturing sheet forming procedures. Additionally, the comparison of the results of experimental and numerical tests for the thickness distribution and the FLD was done according to the design of the tests in Table 4. By observing the results of Table 11, it is found that the results of the simulation and experimental methods are generally in agreement. In the simulation results, in accordance with the experimental results, the lowest value for the thickness distribution occurred in sample 5, which indicates the accurate prediction of the numerical method. Furthermore, sheet number 12 consistently exhibits the lowest formability and experiences the least percentage of thickness reduction in both the experimental and numerical methods. The percentage of prediction error of experimental and numerical methods for thickness distribution is between 9.09 and 12.43; this value is between 11.67 and 14.65 for the FLD. These discrepancies in the results can be attributed to factors such as the simplification of the finite element model, the material properties of the sheet, constraints within the rolling system, and the friction coefficient between the tool and the sheet [36].

Table 11. The comparison of results extracted from numerical simulation and experimental result.

Test number	Minimum experimental thickness (mm)	Minimum thickness-numerical (mm)	Minimum thickness error percentage (%)	Maximum principal strain-experimental (FLD0)	Maximum principal strain-numerical (FLD0)	FLD0 error percentage (%)
1	0.77	0.693	10.00	0.494	0.433	12.35
2	0.74	0.671	9.32	0.521	0.459	11.90
4	0.81	0.716	11.60	0.428	0.371	13.32
5	0.72	0.643	10.69	0.532	0.462	13.16

6	0.74	0.663	10.40	0.520	0.457	12.12
7	0.81	0.711	12.22	0.411	0.353	14.11
8	0.79	0.694	12.15	0.440	0.378	14.09
9	0.78	0.683	12.43	0.464	0.396	14.65
10	0.84	0.736	12.38	0.407	0.350	14.00
11	0.84	0.742	11.66	0.393	0.341	13.23
12	0.88	0.800	9.09	0.317	0.280	11.67
13	0.87	0.772	11.26	0.322	0.282	12.42
14	0.86	0.769	10.58	0.366	0.321	12.29

5- Conclusion

The findings derived from this research can be summarized as follows:

- By adding the Ti sheet to the aluminum sheet and producing a 3-layer sheet, the tensile strength and formability of the 3-layer sample increased compared to the Al base sheet.
- Upon constructing forming limit diagrams, it was observed that an increase in the step-down results in a shift of strains on the FLD toward the plane strain line. Conversely, reducing the step-down causes strains to gravitate towards the two-axis strain. Consequently, a smaller step-down is more conducive to achieving an optimal strain distribution, albeit with a relatively minor impact on sheet formability compared to the tool diameter parameter. It is important to note that increasing the tool step also leads to an extended processing time.
- After analyzing the thickness distribution across the samples, it became evident that the thinnest regions were at the end of the tool's path. Thinning and cracking phenomena were observed in this terminal region of the sheet's wall.
- By employing variance analysis for the FLD_0 response, it was discerned that the tool diameter factor had a more pronounced impact on the FLD_0 level than the other two factors. To elucidate further, an increase in the tool diameter from 6 millimeters to 9 millimeters resulted in a higher FLD_0 value and, consequently, an enhancement in formability. In simpler terms, the increase in formability was attributed to the larger contact area between the tool and the sheet, localized frictional heating, and the subsequent reduction in forming forces when the tool diameter was expanded to 9 millimeters. Nevertheless, upon further enlargement of the tool diameter to 12 millimeters, localized deformation during the process decreased. This reduction was primarily due to the redistribution of forming forces and localized heat between the tool and the sheet, ultimately overcoming the triaxial stresses. Notably, this decrease in localized deformation resulted from the deformation mechanism inherent to the gradual forming process, which relies on localized deformations and strains.

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- The progressive forming process was simulated using the finite element method, and the outcomes were verified against experimental data. In industrial contexts, a suitable safety factor can be applied to the numerical results derived from the finite element method, thereby facilitating time and cost savings while preserving result reliability.
- Analysis of both experimental findings and numerical simulations revealed that the most significant achievable forming depth, and consequently, the most significant forming angle, were linked to the sheet subjected to a feed rate of 500 millimeters per minute, a tool step of 0.2, and a tool diameter of 9 millimeters. Conversely, the least formability and forming angle were associated with the sheet tested under a 700 millimeters per minute feed rate, a tool step of 1, and a tool diameter of 12 millimeters.

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